

ENHANCING CULTURE THROUGH SOCIAL COMPETENCIES IN OLDER CHILDREN IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Preschool education is the primary stage of organizing the foundation of society. The upbringing of older children in preschool education is a delicate process that requires a special approach. Nowadays, the implementation of cultural competencies in older children through social competencies is a priority for preschool education. There is no doubt that a child who embodies culture will determine the culture of the next generation.

In the commentary to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 30, 2017 No PR-5198 "On measures to completely improve the management of the preschool education system" children in preschool education are taught national and universal values, humanity and upbringing in the sense of high spirituality, independence in their hearts and minds, deepening the idea of national identity, the implementation of measures aimed at strengthening immunity against foreign ideas in the form of "popular culture". .

Indeed, in order to become a harmoniously developed person for the younger generation, it is necessary to be aware of the people, the history of the homeland, and the experience of their ancestors in the field of education, to build a culture by saturating social competencies.

It includes patriotism based on national pride, national values, sense of agreement and solidarity. The stronger is for love and pride for the motherland in the younger generation, the stronger is for love

and respect for the Motherland, the stronger the history, national values, native language, culture, national traditions of each person, independence will be so strong and stable if he knows his customs and traditions perfectly, have a deep understanding of the fate and future of the nation.

-National pride is the feeling of belonging to a particular nation and the contribution that nation has made to world culture, as well as a sense of devotion to one's own nation and practical action in that direction.

The constant influence in family upbringing is family relations, family environment, and interaction of family members, behavior of parents, siblings and others, cultural and political level, culture of behavior, family income, living conditions, other circumstances are significant factors influencing child development. The more disciplined, well-mannered, and sincere the relationship between its members, the more effective the family upbringing will be.

Imam ibn Kudama, in his book Minhaj al-Qasidin, mentions a number of etiquettes: the child should be well observed and aware of the condition of him when the child grows up and his mental symptom appears. Because a child's heart is simple and pure, he is ready to accept any methods. If you get used to positives, you will grow up with it. If he gets used to negatives, he will grow up with it and the responsibility will be up to his relatives. "

The future development of adult children in preschool depends in many ways on the educator of the preschool, the people closest to him: the culture of interaction between parents, the relationship.

The use of special forms and methods, based on the program called "Bolajon", is the result of a two-pronged effort, which is directly dependent on educators and parents, to build a culture of social competences in older adults in preschools. That is why we offer the following recommendations for educators and parents.

- It is important that educators have good manners, pedagogical knowledge, and constantly improve their skills;

- It is necessary to take a serious approach to the process of formation of national feelings in preschool children, to pay attention to the demonstration of their abilities;

- In the process of forming national feelings in preschool children, conducting their assessment, it is necessary to allow children to feel free and comfortable;

- Questions and assignments for older children in preschool education institutions should have a clear purpose of education and meet the educational content in terms of size and complexity;

- Educational activities in preschools should also be innovative and interesting for today's children;

- Classes should be conducted through excursions, trips, interviews, debates, educational activities, depending on the interests of older children in the institution.

- It is advisable to carry out ideological education with the parents of older children in preschool education;

- It is recommendable to establish training centers and regular seminars for parents with children to work with parents to help them, become healthy, well-rounded, nationally proud people expedient;

At the behind of the above ideas is the formation of national pride in preschool children, their preparation for social life, to be proud of the Motherland and to serve it, to be well-rounded people.

The main goal of the education system today, as in all spheres, is to bring up our children, who are growing up, in the spirit of humanity and patriotism. At the same time, it is necessary to educate the younger generation on the basis of the rich and unique history of our national traditions. As the child grows older, social life adapts to the world around him.

Preschool education requires the introduction of a humane approach to personal education based on the wealthy spiritual and intellectual heritage of the people and universal values. It also includes patriotism formed on the basis of national feelings, a sense of pride, national values, agreement and solidarity. The stronger the love and pride for the motherland in the younger generation, the stronger the love and respect for the Motherland, the stronger the history, national values, native language,

culture, national traditions of each person, independence will be so strong and stable if he knows his customs and traditions perfectly, has a deep understanding of the fate and future of the nation.

The process of the child is based on the attitude of the individual to the environment, community, family, national and secular relations, and at the same time perceives society through the worldview of the being, the consciousness formed in it.

At first glance, this process may seem simple in terms of the social environment, but at the international level, if we look at the example of different countries, you can see that ethnic education is emerging in different forms. In this regard, our country, with its

historical culture and spirituality, national traditions and values, reflects the thousand-year history of the Uzbek people.

Teachers and educators regularly hold talks with parents; acquaint them with the content and methods of their work on the education of children, and should use the positive examples of family education in their educational work.

Fostering independence in older children in preschool education, the formation of cultural habits, relationships with peers and adults, the formation of a culture of activity, the development of a careful attitude to objects, the goodness of children's age are essential to form such moral concepts as honesty, truthfulness, courage, humility.

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